

Field amelioration of an acid sulfate soil for rice with manganese dioxide and lime

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The effects of manganese dioxide (100 kg/ha) and lime (5 t/ha) on iron toxicity symptoms and yield of IR26 and IR43 on a flooded, acid sulfate soil (a Sulfaquept whose characteristics are in Table 1) were studied in a replicated factorial experiment in a farmer's field in Malinao, Albay, Philippines.

On the basis of iron toxicity symptoms 4 and 8 weeks after transplanting, the best treatment had lime and manganese dioxide and the moderately tolerant IR43. The poorest had the moderately susceptible IR26 but without lime or manganese dioxide (Table 2). Analysis of variance of the symptoms' scores revealed no significant response to lime, but a significant difference between the two varieties and a highly significant, positive response to manganese dioxide.

On the basis of grain yield, the best treatment had IR43 and manganese dioxide, with or without lime (Table 2). The poorest had IR26 without lime and manganese dioxide. Analysis of variance revealed a nonsignificant response to lime, a highly significant varietal difference, a highly Significant positive response to manganese dioxide, and a highly significant variety and manganese dioxide interaction (Table 3).

IR26 gave a response of 1.2 t/ha to manganese dioxide in the presence of lime. IR43 showed a response of 2.2 t/ha

Table 2. Effects of lime and manganese dioxide on the severity of iron toxicity symptoms 4 and 8 weeks after transplanting, and on grain yield of 2 rice varieties on an acid sulfate soil. Malinao, Albay, Philippines, 1980 dry season.^a

Treatment			Iron toxicity score ^b		Yield (t/ha)
Lime	Manganese dioxide	Variety	4 wk after transplanting	8 wk after transplanting	
No	No	IR26	5.8 d	6.0 a	3.6 d
No	Yes	IR26	4.8 cd	5.2 ab	3.9 d
No	No	IR43	4.8 cd	5.5 ab	4.0 cd
No	Yes	IR43	3.5 ab	4.2 bc	6.2 a
Yes	No	IR26	5.2 cd	5.8 a	4.3 cd
Yes	Yes	IR26	4.2 bc	4.8 ab	4.8 bc
Yes	No	IR43	3.5 ab	4.2 bc	5.3 b
Yes	Yes	IR43	3.0 a	4.0 c	6.2 a

^aAny two means in a column followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level. ^bOn the scale 1 to 9 based on foliar symptoms and general appearance (1 = nearly normal plants, 9 = dead or nearly dead plants).

Table 3. Analysis of variance for grain yield from the acid sulfate soil amelioration plots. Malinao, Albay, Philippines, 1980 dry season.

sv	df	SS	MS	F(obs)
Block	3	2.601	0.867	
Lime (L)	1	4.100	4.100	5.04 ^{ns}
Error a	3	0.814	0.271	
Variety (V)	1	13.120	13.120	16.84**
L x V	1	0.061	0.061	<1 ^{ns}
Error b	6	4.674	0.779	
Manganese dioxide (M)	1	7.576	7.576	24.52**
L x M	1	0.567	0.567	1.83 ^{ns}
V x M	1	3.032	3.032	9.81**
L x V x M	1	1.050	1.050	3.40 ^{ns}
Error c	12	3.711	0.309	
Total	31	41.306		
CV (a) = 10.82%		CV (b) = 18.35%		CV (c) = 11.56%
s.e. = 0.28				

to manganese dioxide in the absence of lime. In the presence of manganese dioxide, lime increased the yield of IR26 by 0.90 t/ha, but in the absence of manganese dioxide, IR43 gave a response of 1.3 t/ha with lime.

The benefits from manganese dioxide

are attributed to manganese which, assisted by lime, counteracts physiologically the toxic effects of excess iron. Manganese dioxide, coupled with the tolerant variety and lime, may be an inexpensive ameliorant for acid sulfate soils. ■

Table 1. Some chemical characteristics of the soil at the experimental site, Malinao, Albay, Philippines.

pH of dry soil (1:1 H ₂ O)	3.5
EC _e (mmho/cm)	1.0
CEC (meq/100 g)	9.5
Organic C (%)	1.23
Total N (%)	0.15
Active Fe (%)	2.50
Active Mn (%)	0.001
Exchangeable K ⁺ (meq/100 g)	0.17
Exchangeable SO ₄ ²⁻ (%)	0.27
Available (Olsen) P (ppm)	7.0

Influence of continuous submergence on the kinetics of pH, Eh, and Ec in some acid soils of Assam

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The effect of continuous submergence on the kinetics of electrochemical properties

was studied on four typical rice-growing acid soils of Assam in the laboratory.

Continuous submergence brought about significant electrochemical changes in the soil (see table). Within a period of 10 to 15 days after submergence, pH increased significantly, creating an almost neutral soil condition, accompanied by a decrease in Eh and an increase in Ec. The treatment created a favorable soil environment for growing rice. ■